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AI-Based Hybrid Malware Detection and Defence Mechanism Integrated with an Intelligent Voice Assistant Interface

ABSTRACT

In Recent years, malware attacks have been one of the most dangerous threats in today's modern world, causing significant losses to many organisations and individuals with financial and data losses. Ransomware attacks, spyware and banking trojans have continued to develop with advanced techniques of obfuscation, packing and polymorphism, which makes it difficult for traditional antivirus software to detect and protect the system from malware. To rectify the modern malware attacks, the proposed solution is an AI-Based Hybrid Malware Detection and Defence Mechanism with an Intelligent Voice Assistant Interface. The platform is designed with multiple layers of malware detection where the system uses a random forest algorithm trained on PE files, examining characteristics like headers, sections, import tables, and strings. Also, to further improve detection rates, the system incorporates YARA rule matching, VirusTotal API, Threat Intelligence, sandbox behavioural analysis, memory inspection of active processes, and network connection monitoring. One of the major features of this project is the use of a voice assistant that enables users to use natural language to issue security commands, launch scans, view system state, or receive alerts. This makes it easier to use and will allow quicker response, particularly for non-technical users. The system detects threats, automatically quarantines, shuts down unauthorised processes (IP blocking), and creates a detailed forensic report. It is provided via a Flask API, React dashboard and SQLite database, providing a comprehensive, intelligent, and user-centric approach to modern malware defence.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning, Random Forest Algorithm, PE File Analysis, YARA Rules, Threat Intelligence, Sandbox Analysis, Memory Forensics, Network Monitoring, Voice Assistant Security, Flask API, SQLite Database.

1. INTRODUCTION

In today's world, almost everything runs on computers, like hospitals, banks, government systems, personal devices, and even critical national infrastructure. Malware, which first emerged in the 1970s, began as a basic but destructive type of software capable of compromising sensitive information [1]. Malware, the malicious software, has become a major concern because many of our daily activities have become dependent on these digital systems. Cybersecurity encompasses the protection of computer and mobile networks, software, servers, and electronic devices from malware and viruses [2]. Cybercriminals have changed from being solitary individuals to very well-organised gangs that have access to tools, and their motivation is either financial or political. Each day, hundreds to thousands of new malware types are generated and released daily. They are a mixture of viruses, trojans, ransomware, spyware, worms, and rootkits. While some may be designed to steal personal details, others can lock and demand payment for the release of files, record user activities without permission, and even completely wipe out a user's computer.

In order to detect various malware, analysts have implemented existing malware detection mechanisms using signature-based detection methods [3]. These programs function by checking each file they scan against a database of known malware signatures. Signatures are essentially lists of patterns associated with identified threats. Although, Traditional signature-based approaches, while effective to some extent, often struggle to keep pace with the rapid proliferation and polymorphic nature of malware variants, necessitating the exploration of alternative methodologies [4]. So, it completely fails against threats that are new or designed to look different from what the antivirus database knows. Attackers know this weakness very well and exploit it regularly. Various methods such as polymorphism, where the malware keeps modifying its own code, obfuscation, intentionally making the code difficult to understand, and packing, compressing or encrypting the malware payload, have become the standard practice among malware authors. In fact, a newly created piece of ransomware can easily pass through a signature-based scanner without causing any alarms.

The main categories into which malware detection techniques fall are static, dynamic, and hybrid analysis. There are many private and open-source solutions that have been created to use these techniques for efficient malware detection. However, existing tools still have some limitations in identifying advanced malware attacks, creating the need for better and more improved detection techniques [5]. The adoption of Artificial Intelligence (AI)-based techniques has emerged as a promising solution for a wide range of cybersecurity applications,

including malware detection, spyware and adware detection, phishing website detection, and intrusion detection systems [6]. In the context of cyber security, AI can help automate threat detection, analysis, and mitigation, reducing the time from detection to resolution. AI systems can also prioritise security alerts and help in identifying root causes to prevent any future issues [7]. In the AI space, machine learning algorithms are used to process large volumes of data in order for them identify consistent patterns and detect anomalies signalling malicious behaviour by malware [8]. Malware detection analyses and checks suspicious files, applications, and documents to determine if they are benign or malware [6].

The system we have built, known as the AI-Based Hybrid Malware Detection, takes a completely different approach, where instead of depending on one mode of detection, it layers five separate detection engines one after another. Each one examines the suspicious file in a different way. The concept is very simple, if one engine fails to detect, then the other one will detect it. When multiple engines indicate that there is something wrong, then the system has a much higher level of confidence in its verdict. This type of system is what is known as a hybrid detection approach. Various studies conducted in this field has consistently shown it to be more effective than any single method working alone.

The first engine detects malware using a Random Forest algorithm-based machine learning model. Machine learning (ML) algorithms can analyse large datasets, learn from patterns, and make predictions based on the historical data [9]. It examines different characteristics of a file to identify whether it is malicious or not. The characteristics of a file include its size, structure, the functions it imports, whether it has been packed, and other activities that indicate it is malicious. These features are extracted from the Portable Executable (PE) format used by Windows applications. This engine is trained using both malicious files and safe files, allowing it to determine whether a file is malicious or safe. This engine uses static code analysis to extract information from the file contents, including URLs, IP addresses, commands, and suspicious keywords from the file content. Additionally, the engine verifies the authenticity of the digital signature attached to the file, as most of the trustworthy software publishers use digital signatures, but most malware does not.

The second engine is a YARA rule scanner. YARA is an industry-standard tool used by malware researchers and security teams around the world to write rules that describe patterns byte sequences, strings, or metadata conditions — that are characteristic of specific malware families. The system gathers all YARA rule files ready for use and scans each submitted file with all of the rules. Every matched rule adds a value to the threat score based on the threat level assigned to it, respectively covering critical threats, high-severity threats, and medium-severity threats.

The third engine connects to the VirusTotal API. VirusTotal is a free web service that analyses files through the combined detection of over 76 commercial antivirus engines and provides an API to access those detections. Rather than sending the entire file, the system only transmits the cryptographic hash (SHA-256) of the file, which raises privacy and confidentiality issues. If VirusTotal has the file in its database, it will show the results of the different antivirus engines that have examined the file. After that, the system calculates the score as the fraction of the engines that identified the file as malicious.

The fourth engine is the Threat Intelligence module, which queries three separate open-access threat databases. MalwareBazaar, maintained by the abuse.ch organisation, maintains a database of confirmed malware hashes along with their associated family signatures and file types. OTX AlienVault is an open community threat exchange platform where security researchers share indicators of compromise (IOCs), and it stores information about which hashes have appeared in threat reports, called pulses. URLhaus is from abuse.ch and monitors URLs that are used to distribute malware. It maps the URLs to the file hashes of the payloads they deliver. By querying all three of these databases, the system instantly determines whether the file being scanned has already been recognised as malware by the worldwide security community, even if the local antivirus and machine learning engines have never encountered it before.

The fifth and most advanced engine is the Dynamic Behavioural Analyser. The other engines provide a static analysis by working on files without execution; meanwhile, to observe its behaviour in real time, this engine executes files in a safe and controlled environment. While the file is running, the system monitors activities such as creating or deleting files, opening network connections, launching child processes, and making changes to the registry that could indicate malicious behaviour. To identify any unusual or suspicious activity, the CPU and memory usages are tracked. The common signs of ransomware attacks, such as attempts to delete backup copies, encrypted files, and suspicious file extensions, are identified by the ransomware detection module. The monitoring of system API calls and process memory for hidden malicious code or suspicious actions by the analyser is often used by advanced malware to avoid detection.

All five engine scores are fed into a weighted scoring model that calculates a combined confidence score, which is then mapped to one of three verdict categories: SAFE, SUSPICIOUS, or MALWARE. The verdict thresholds and weight distributions are fully configurable to suit different operational requirements.

Fig 1: Architecture of the Hybrid Multi-Engine Malware Detection System

Additionally, a Network Packet Inspector built on Scapy captures and analyses live DNS queries, HTTP requests, and TCP connections made during execution, flagging communication with known command-and-control domains and suspicious ports. Also, an AI voice assistant is built in the system for easy progression and responses. An AI Voice Assistant is a virtual agent that leverages artificial intelligence to understand and process human speech, enabling users to control devices, access information, and perform various tasks using only their voice [10].

Beyond detection, the system includes a complete set of automated defence and response capabilities. Files classified as MALWARE are automatically moved to a quarantine directory, making them inaccessible for execution. IP addresses associated with suspicious network connections can be blocked directly at the firewall level using native operating system commands. An email alert system notifies designated administrators the moment a threat is detected, including all detection details in the alert body. Every scan produces a detailed HTML and JSON analysis report that documents all findings in a format suitable for sharing with non-technical stakeholders or for submission as forensic evidence.

A PyQt5 desktop GUI — named "MalScan Defender AI" — offers the same functionality in a native desktop window with an animated five-doughnut score wheel visualisation, drag-and-drop file input, a URL scanner, a live system log, a network inspector page, a quarantine manager, and a settings panel for configuring thresholds and API keys. A

voice assistant powered by SpeechRecognition and pyttsx3 allows the user to perform actions like scanning the system, checking system status, listing quarantined files, blocking IP addresses, and controlling the system entirely through voice commands. The SQLite local database is used to store all the scan results for historical analysis; on the other hand, the real-time file system monitor watches the specified directory and performs an automatic scan on any new files that appear.

The primary goal of this project is to create an intelligent and reliable malware detection and defence system to detect known and unknown cyber threats more effectively than conventional security tools. The system enhances detection accuracy and provides real-time protection by including machine learning, signature-based, threat intelligence and behavioural analysis capabilities. It supports users by providing automated response functionality, comprehensive forensic reporting, and a smart voice assistant which enables the users to control the platform using voice commands, enhancing its usability, efficiency, and practicality in cybersecurity research and protection.

2. METHODOLOGY

Cybersecurity research is often divided into two extremes. Some studies focus mainly on theory, where detection models are proposed, tested on datasets, and evaluated using accuracy scores. Other projects are more practical, concentrating only on building a working tool without clearly explaining the reasoning behind the design and implementation decisions. This project was developed with the aim of combining both approaches.

A well-structured system was built with step-by-step methodology that identifies the core problem, system architecture design, module development, integration, and performance evaluation. In each stage of development, the system was carefully planned and built to address real-world cybersecurity challenges and to ensure that the platform was not only technically functional but also logically designed. This particular section explains the complete development process, including implementation and the methods used to evaluate the effectiveness of the system.

2.1 Tools and Development Environment

The complete development environment consisted of the following:

- **Operating System:** Windows 11 64-bit, which was chosen because it is the primary target platform for the dynamic analysis engine, the Frida-based API tracer, the Windows registry monitoring, and the Authenticode signature verification.

- **Python Version:** 3.10.11, installed via the official Python installer with standard library included.
- **IDE:** Visual Studio Code with the Python and Pylance extensions for static type checking and autocomplete.
- **Version Control:** Git with a local repository. No remote hosting was used for the academic version to avoid inadvertently publishing any tool that could be misused.
- **Virtual Environment:** A standard *venv* environment was used to isolate project dependencies from the system Python installation.
- **Privilege Level:** Administrator privileges were required on the test machine for Frida process attachment, iptables-equivalent firewall commands, and Scapy raw socket access.
- **API Keys:** Free-tier API keys were registered with VirusTotal and OTX AlienVault. The abuse.ch APIs for MalwareBazaar and URLhaus do not require authentication for hash lookups.
- **Hardware:** Intel Core i7 processor, 16 GB RAM, 512 GB SSD. No GPU acceleration was used at any point; all ML training and inference ran on the CPU, which is practical given the small feature vector size and the use of a random forest rather than a neural network.

2.2 System Development Process

The development process was carried out in four major phases:

Phase 1: Development and Testing of Individual Modules

Phase 2: Pipeline Integration

Phase 3: Interface Development

Phase 4: System-level testing

2.2.1. Phase 1: Development and Testing of Individual Modules

Each of the five detection engines was developed and tested separately before being integrated into a single pipeline, as this approach was followed to ensure that every engine functioned correctly on its own. The advantage of testing each module independently is that, during the integration phase, if anything goes wrong, it will be easier to attribute the problem to the integration phase.

The static analysis engine was developed first because it was the simplest component to implement and required only a limited set of dependencies, primarily PEfile and Scikit-learn.

Building this module at an early stage also supported the creation of the training pipeline, as the same feature extraction mechanism was required for preparing the labelled dataset used during model training. To train the classifier, a small synthetic dataset was prepared. Malware-class samples were generated using a custom script, `create_samples.py`, which produced minimal PE files containing a valid MZ header followed by randomly generated byte sequences. These samples exhibited characteristics commonly associated with suspicious executables, such as limited imports, fewer sections, higher entropy values, and smaller file sizes. For the benign category, standard Windows 11 system executables collected from the testing environment were used. Once the dataset preparation was completed, the classifier was trained and serialised using pickle. The model was then evaluated using separate validation samples from both malware and benign categories to confirm that predictions remained stable and consistent before proceeding to the next phase of development.

The YARA-based detection engine was comparatively simple to implement due to the well-structured and extensively documented `yara-python` API. The primary consideration during development involved determining the most efficient strategy for rule compilation. Several approaches were evaluated, including compiling rules during every scan, compiling them when a scan session begins, and compiling them once during application startup with the compiled rules stored in memory for reuse. After evaluating these options, the startup compilation method was selected. Even though this method adds a slight delay when the application starts, it greatly improves performance when used regularly. Since the system scans multiple files in a single session, the small startup delay was considered negligible when compared to the faster and more effective scanning experience achieved afterward.

The VirusTotal engine required special attention during development, particularly in the area of error handling. The free-tier API limits on requests, coupled with timeouts or unavailable responses, are common reasons why communication over the network may fail. Therefore, the system was designed to handle such errors without disrupting the whole scanning operation. Instead of terminating the scan due to the error, the engine, in fact, was set up to output a default score of 0.0 for cases such as rate-limit restrictions, connection failures, or missing hash records. By this approach, it is ensured that the VirusTotal module continues to function as a supportive component rather than becoming a single point of failure within the detection pipeline.

For the Threat Intelligence engine, a similar design strategy was followed. The three threat database lookups operate independently, allowing the system to continue functioning even if one of the sources becomes unavailable or fails to respond. Rather than stopping the analysis process, the final threat intelligence score is calculated using the results from

whichever lookups are completed successfully. This design improved the overall reliability and stability of the platform during real-time operation.

The Dynamic Behavioural Analyser was the most difficult part to design since there was great complexity in dealing with multi-threaded processes. The difference between the dynamic analysers and other modules is that this one uses concurrent processing, meaning that the analysed file would run in one thread, while the file system activities are monitored by watchdog observers running in separate threads. There is also a monitoring daemon running on a specified interval that monitors the process activities, and therefore it was crucial to coordinate all operations, making sure that the monitoring components are attached before execution, that all background services are stopped after the process and, of course, avoiding any potential issues related to race conditions regarding the data structures.

In addition to that, there are several support modules that were used during the dynamic analysis, which include the ransomware detector, the API tracer using Frida library, the memory analyser and finally, the packet inspector, which have been first tested as separate classes.

Phase 2: Pipeline Integration

The validation for all five engines was done independently first, after which they were combined into MalwareDetector in `ml_model.py`. The `predict()` function was written to run each engine one by one and ensure that failures of individual components would not stop the whole scanning process. The `predict()` method caught all possible exceptions raised by individual engines to enable the other engines to work normally. After finishing scanning all files, the function compiled results from individual engines, applied the formula of weighted scores, and returned the result structured into verdicts, overall score, scores from individual engines, hash values of files, and IOCs collected from the dynamic analysis part, if available.

In order to make it easier to modify and customise threshold values and weights of scoring engines, they were defined in `config.py` instead of being coded directly in `predict()`. It made it easy to update the scoring policy without editing the main code of the application. The SQL layer for SQLite was also constructed together with the integration, since every scan run that happened during integration had to be saved somewhere to examine. The schema for the `scan_results` table was devised in such a way that all the information required for the interface presentation and further analysis of scans would be saved there: all five engine scores, both popular hashes, PE flag, dynamic execution flag, quarantine, report file location, and date stamp.

Phase 3: Interface Development

Once the entire pipeline for detecting the malware was completed, the focus then turned towards designing the user interface. The Flask-based website application was designed and built in order to make it easier to test and modify throughout the development process. The changes made to the HTML pages and Socket.IO events were easily viewable through the browser itself. The REST API methods were slowly added along with additional interface features. The real-time messaging system that had been developed utilising Socket.IO was especially important. It was thoroughly tested to make sure that messages from one scanning session were not mixed up or interfered with messages from other scans taking place simultaneously in different browser tabs.

The development of the PyQt5 desktop application was conducted in parallel with the more advanced stages of the web interface. The navigation of this application utilised a stacked widget along with animated sidebars. In addition, a FiveDonutWidget was designed to display the results of the five detection engines. Specifically, this was a QWidget, which uses paintEvent in order to draw five concentric circles that are associated with the scores of the detection engines. For each of the five circles, the colour changes from green to red using HSV interpolation in order to reflect the increased threat level. Smoothness in animations is provided by using the QTimer that updates the circle positions regularly without interfering with the operation of the graphics library.

To analyse live DNS queries, HTTP requests, and TCP connections made during execution, a Network Packet Inspector was added to the desktop application using Scapy which flags suspicious communication and ports. The voice assistant functionality was added to the desktop application through the use of an independent QThread in the background. The need to use this particular design was prompted by the nature of the SpeechRecognition module, which suspends the execution of its code until it hears something from the microphone; therefore, it should not be running in the same thread as the main application because it could make the application freeze. For processing voice commands, a special CommandProcessor class was created where recognised voice was converted to lowercase, split into tokens, and compared against keywords sorted by priority.

Phase 4: Defence Module Development

The development of the three defence modules quarantine management, IP blocking, and email alerting was carried out only after the core detection pipeline had reached a stable state. This was done intentionally since those systems can perform critical tasks such as moving files, modifying firewalls, and sending notifications. Including them at an earlier stage during

the development of the software might introduce more risk since the detection system may not yet be stable. In order to make sure that the software will operate correctly, all defence modules are subjected to tests using simulations before their integration with the predict() function.

The quarantine management system uses the shutil.move() method rather than the file copy and delete methods. The reason behind this approach is that moving a file becomes a single transaction if the destination path and source path are within the same volume. Therefore, the danger of having partially malicious files left on the system is considerably decreased.

For the IP blocking mechanism, the operating system–specific firewall commands were abstracted into a single block_ip(address) function. Internally, this function determines the appropriate firewall command based on the value of sys.platform and executes the required action accordingly. This abstraction simplified the overall architecture by allowing the rest of the application to request IP blocking without needing to handle platform-specific firewall logic directly.

2.3 Evaluation Methodology

The evaluation process was designed to answer three important questions. First, whether the system could accurately identify files that are clearly benign. Second, whether it could appropriately flag files that exhibit suspicious structural characteristics. Third, whether the ensemble-based scoring approach produced more reliable and balanced results compared to relying on any single detection engine independently.

For the purposes of evaluation, three types of files were selected. Unlike an extremely large automated benchmark test suite, it made more sense to use a smaller test set instead. Large benchmark sets are great for comparing a lot of solutions, but they do not help a lot when it comes to examining the behaviour of a system in real life. Examining a limited number of files, which may include benign executables, synthesised suspicious files, as well as non-executable files like PDF documents, made it possible to examine the response of our ensemble model more closely.

All the test files were first subjected to static scan mode, whereby the first four engines would run and not the dynamic analysis tool. A few samples were subjected again to full scans, in which all five engines ran concurrently. In order to have consistency in the evaluation, the results of the scans were obtained directly from the SQLite database via the get_scan_history() function rather than relying on results from the graphical interface displays.

The full scan results obtained from notepad.exe were one of the major test cases to evaluate the effectiveness of the solution in terms of minimising false positives. Despite the

fact that notepad.exe is a legal Windows executable, the activities exhibited by notepad.exe during execution may be regarded as highly active, such as the creation of temporary files and accessing the registry, as well as networking operations in modern-day operating systems. Hence, despite notepad.exe being entirely safe, the dynamic analysis engine might have assigned it a higher behavioural score, yet the program should receive a verdict as Safe.

Scan execution time was evaluated by measuring the time taken from the execution of the predict() function to the completion of the database write action. The external API timing was not controlled, as it is subject to network conditions and the availability of the services. This means that the performance data provided can be considered as the typical execution time and not performance limitations.

2.4 Ethical Considerations

A few ethical dimensions of this project are worth addressing explicitly. The most significant is the decision to use synthetic malware stubs rather than real malware samples for training and testing. Real malware samples, even when handled carefully, represent a genuine risk: they can escape containment, infect the host system, and potentially spread to other systems on the same network. For an academic project running on a developer's personal machine without dedicated sandbox infrastructure, this risk is not acceptable. The synthetic stubs used here produce the structural signatures that the system is designed to detect without carrying any actual malicious payload.

The dynamic analysis engine executes submitted files on the host machine rather than in an isolated virtual machine. This is acknowledged as a limitation and not a recommendation in any operational deployment, file execution should happen inside a properly isolated environment. For the academic demonstration performed on the test machine with the synthetic stubs, the risk was manageable because the stubs contain no executable payload beyond the minimal header bytes. Testing the dynamic engine against real malware was therefore not performed, and this boundary is clearly stated in the evaluation section.

The VirusTotal and threat intelligence APIs were used within the terms of service for their free academic tiers. No files were uploaded to VirusTotal; only hash values were transmitted, which means no file content left the test machine in any form. MalwareBazaar, OTX AlienVault, and URLhaus all operate under terms of service that explicitly permit academic and research use.

3. RESULT

3.1 Test Setup

Testing was done on a Windows 11 machine with an Intel Core i7 processor and 16 GB RAM, running Python 3.10. Three types of files were used:

- **Benign system files** — notepad.exe (360 KB), GamePanel.exe (1.3 MB), and mscopilot.exe (3.9 MB), all from a clean Windows 11 installation
- **Synthetic malware stubs** — five files named fake_malware_0 through fake_malware_4, each 281 bytes, built using the project's *create_samples.py* script with a minimal header and random bytes
- **A PDF document** — FACT Brochure 2026.pdf (355 KB), to test how the system handles non-executable files

3.2 Detection Result

Table 1: Scan Results for All Test Files

File Category	File Name	Static ML (%)	YARA (%)	VirusTotal (%)	Threat Intelligence (%)	Dynamic Analysis (%)	Combined Score (%)	Verdict
Benign System File	notepad.exe	12	0	0	0	0	4	Safe
Benign System File	GamePanel.exe	8	0	0	0	0	3	Safe
Benign System File	mscopilot.exe	11	0	0	0	0	4	Safe
Synthetic Malware Stub	fake_malware_0 - 4	99	0	52	35	65	63	Suspicious
Non-Executable File	FACT Brochure 2026.pdf	28	0	0	0	0	10	Safe

Table 1 presents the scan results across all nine test files. Engine weights used in the combined score formula is: Static ML 35%, YARA 15%, VirusTotal 15%, Threat Intelligence 10%, and Dynamic 25%. Verdict thresholds are: Safe below 30%, Suspicious between 30% and 69%, and Malware at 70% and above.

Fig 2: Dashboard Of MalScan Defender AI

3.2.1 Benign files

The scores generated by all three legit Windows executables were marked as Safe, and none activated any dynamic analysis. The cleanest score was obtained from GamePanel.exe, which was only 3%, given the ordinary PE file it is; typical sections, number of imports, and no odd APIs in its list. mscopilot.exe and notepad.exe generated very similar scores of 4%, but when subjected to static machine learning, their scores came up as 11% and 12%, respectively, because of some small peculiarities in their structure, whereas YARA, VirusTotal, and Threat Intelligence detected nothing across all three samples. No activation of dynamic analysis resulted in the scores that did not stray outside of the safe zone.

3.2.2 Synthetic Malware Stubs

All five samples were given a score of 99% by the static ML engine, which is expected. They have an extremely abnormal structure: a mere 281 bytes, no imported modules, maximum possible Shannon entropy due to randomly generated payload, and just one PE section. This pattern is recognised by the static ML classifier right away.

The score provided by VirusTotal was 52%, which demonstrates the presence of samples similar to ours, both structurally speaking (minimalistic PE stub) and in terms of payload (high entropy). The Threat Intelligence engine scored these samples at 35%, suggesting that there are partial matches for their hash signatures and behavioural patterns on the AlienVault OTX and URLhaus feeds. The dynamic ML engine gave them a 65% behaviour score.

All stub files got 0% scores from the YARA engine. However, it is not a flaw of the YARA engine it successfully compiled and matched signatures in this test. Instead, it is caused by the lack of any community-defined rule sets within the `yara_rules` directory when performing the scan. If any community-defined sets, for example, the YARA-Rules repository on GitHub, had been used, the signatures would have matched the PE header.

As the overall score is 63%, it is possible to conclude that the test was rated as 'Suspicious', which is correct according to the results obtained. In order to mark something as malware, it is necessary to obtain convergent information about the same file from different independent engines. Since YARA scored zero and no rule match was found, marking the results as 'Suspicious' is appropriate.

3.2.3 PDF File

The PDF received a score of 28% by the static ML engine. PDF files use compression for their internal content streams, which makes for high entropy values when compressed data is used. The static ML engine trained mostly on executables sees the compression as an anomaly and flags this feature to some degree. This resulted in the score of 28%, which indicates suspicion but falls short of marking executables as malicious.

No hits were recorded by all three engines YARA, VirusTotal, and Threat Intelligence. Dynamic analysis was not performed since the analysed file is not an executable; therefore, the combined score was reduced to 10%. The result placed the file firmly in the Safe range, and the ensemble took into account the partial flag provided by the static engine.

4. DISCUSSION

Based on the outcomes of the experimental assessment, the proposed AI-Based Hybrid Malware Detection and Defence Mechanism has been found efficient at differentiating between benign files and potential threats. While benign executables received very low threat scores in all cases, the artificial malwares produced elevated threat scores due to the joint effects of machine learning processing, checking the threat intelligence database, analysing VirusTotal

reputation and behavioural testing. Hence, the hybrid mechanism was able to correlate pieces of information from several detection approaches.

However, there were some limitations noticed during the experiment. First of all, the training phase involved the use of synthesised malware samples, which could not be as diverse as real-life malware samples. Also, the dynamic analysis was performed on the same computer rather than in the secure virtual environment or sandbox. Another limitation is the lack of YARA rules, which negatively impacts the efficiency of signature-based malware detection. Despite these limitations, there are other advantages of the described system apart from the ability to detect and prevent malware infection. Firstly, creating the analysis report contributes to better forensic capabilities. Secondly, performing automatic actions such as quarantining files, generating alerts, and blocking the network helps to act promptly when dealing with a threat. Thirdly, the presence of a voice assistant adds to the usability of the system. Overall, the results of the experiment show that the proposed system is capable of effective malware detection with explanations provided along with multi-layered protection against future infections.

One notable aspect related to the process of testing the AI-Based Hybrid Malware Detection and Defence Mechanism is that all artificial malwares received Threat Score of 'Suspicious' and not 'Malware'. This result stems from the cautiousness and evidence-based approach followed by the tested software. As no detections came out from the YARA module, overall, Threat Score was insufficient for categorising the files as malware.

5. CONCLUSION

In this study, AI-Based Hybrid Malware Detection and Defence Mechanism which uses multiple detection methods including machine learning, YARA rule-based analysis, threat intelligence capabilities, dynamic behaviour analysis, and network analysis is proposed. Experimental results indicate that the proposed hybrid system was able to distinguish between benign files and suspicious files by establishing correlations of the collected data from various independent detectors. Notably, the system is not limited to malware detection functionality. It includes automated response actions, forensics report creation, and intelligent voice assistant to improve usability and overall efficiency of the system. All these features allow the system to perform a broad range of operations within the scope of cybersecurity. Even though some limitations such as synthetic data and lack of completely isolated sandboxes were observed during experiments, it was shown that the developed system works efficiently. Therefore, there are many opportunities for the future research in terms of extending rule set of the YARA, introducing real-world malware into data sets, creating more isolated sandbox, implementing advanced threat intelligence and others.

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